

Albumin Assay Kit

(Colorimetric Method)

Serial No: A028-1-1 Pack: 100T/96S

1、 Assay principle (Bromocresol green method):

Albumin is easy to combine with anionic dye. Under condition of pH4.0, bromocresol green combines with albumin and dye's color converts from yellow to green. "Green intensity" appears direct proportion with albumin concentration.

2、 Reagents composition & Preparation (100T/96S)

Reagent 1: Bromocresol green stock solution: 100ml×1 bottle, can be stored at 4℃. When use, dilute stock solution with distilled water at ratio of 1:4 (100ml bromocresol green: 400ml distilled water) to prepare bromocresol green working solution.

Reagent 2: 34.8g/L Standard, 0.3ml×1 vial, can be stored at -20℃.

3、 Operation Procedure

	Blank tube	Standard tube	Sample tube
Distilled water (ml)	0.02		
Albumin standard (ml)		0.02	
Sample (ml)			0.02
Bromocresol green working solution (ml)	5	5	5
Mix sufficiently, place at room temperature for 10 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 628nm (adjust zero by blank tube).			

4、 Calculation

Formula:

$$\text{Albumin content (g/L)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Sample tube}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard tube}}} \times \text{Albumin standard concentration (g/L)}$$

5、 Assay significance:

Albumin is synthesized in liver and its molecular weight is 66450, 40% ~ 60% of total plasma protein is albumin. Albumin's main functions include: sustain vessel colloid osmotic pressure, as nutrition source of endogenous amino acids, as carrier of transferring and storage. Albumin can combine and dilute various matters such as bilirubin, long chain fatty acid, thyroxine, liothyronine, cortisone, aldosterone, etc. Hormones can be transferred to target tissue in inactive form.